

SiC PARTICLES VOLUME FRACTION INFLUENCE ON FATIGUE CRACK PROPAGATION IN Al-Si METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: Metal matrix composites mechanical properties are strongly dependent on the microstructure and on the characteristics and the properties of the dispersed particles. The base materials, the manufacturing modalities, the heat treatment influence the final microstructure. In this work, the SiC particles volume fraction influence on fatigue crack propagation has been investigated considering an Al-Si based alloy. Different microstructures corresponding to the different SiC volume fractions have been also investigated by means of both optical and scanning electron microscope, using secondary electron emission and the electron back scattering.

KEYWORDS: fatigue crack propagation, SiC particles volume fraction, fatigue fracture surface

INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites have been developed with the aim to obtain lighter materials with high specific strength and stiffness. These properties are particularly interesting in the aerospace industry. Aluminium based MMCs reinforced using particles or whiskers can be considered when not extreme properties are required, thanks to their relatively low cost. Their advantages are usually connected to their isotropy in mechanical properties and the use of conventional metallurgical processes for the allowing fabrication. SiC particles are commonly used as reinforcing material thanks to its good thermal conductivity and chemical compatibility with aluminium [1].

In this paper a 10 or 20 volume percent of added SiC particles eutectic Al-Si based MMC have been investigated, both analysing the microstructure and investigating the influence of SiC volume fraction on fatigue crack propagation.

EXPERIMENTAL MATERIALS AND TECHNIQUES

Chemical composition of the metal matrix and mechanical properties of investigated MMC both with 10 and with 20 volume % are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Matrix chemical composition (wt.%; the Al is rest) [2] and mechanical properties for MMCs with 10 and 20 vol.% SiC particles.

	Si	Fe	Cu	Mn	Mg	Ni	Ti	Zn	Others
Min.	9.5	0.8	3.0	0.5	0.3	1.0	0.0	0.00	0.03
Max.	10.5	1.2	3.5	0.8	0.5	1.5	0.2	0.03	0.10
		σ_y [MPa]			σ_{UTS} [MPa]			A%	
	F3D.10S	152			241			1.2	
	F3D.20S	186			303			0.8	

SiC particles have been injected during the pressure die casting process with a nominal volume fraction of 10 and 20. MMC has been cast in plates measuring about 12.7x140x140 mm. Specimens machining has been difficult: very hard SiC particles quickly blunted the saws. A water jet with a slow jet feed rate of 17 mm/min has been used to cut specimens followed by milling, hand grinding and polishing. Similar difficulties have been encountered in the preparation of sections for microstructural studies and WDX phase analyses: diamond grinding paste had to be used.

MMCs fatigue crack propagation has been investigated according to ASTM E647 standard, using a computer controlled INSTRON 8501 servohydraulic machine in constant load amplitude conditions. Tests have been done in laboratory conditions, at a frequency of 20 Hz, with a sinusoidal waveform, considering a stress ratio of 0.5 (i.e. R). Crack lengths have been measured using both a compliance method with a double cantilever crack mouth gauge and an optical method with a x40 magnification. CT (Compact Type) specimens have been utilised, with the notch obtained via electroerosion.

In order to control the results repeatability, fatigue tests have been repeated three times with the same test conditions.

Fracture surface have been observed using a scanning electron microscopy (SEM) with EDX analysis.

MICROSTRUCTURE

Microstructure reveals a strongly non-uniform SiC distribution at and close to the surface of both the considered composites [3]. In the middles of the specimens the SiC distribution uniformity is higher.

Secondary electron emission and electron back scattering techniques allowed to characterise the MMC microstructure.

Matrix microstructure is very fine grained, with a matrix grain size of about 15.7 μm and 13.6 μm respectively for the 10 and the 20 SiC percent. During solidification, SiC particles are preferential nucleation sites [4], so the high quantity of SiC particles implies a little matrix

grain size. Moreover, microstructure shows particles resembling Chinese script [5], large rounded particles, a grey background composed only by aluminium (the dendrites of the matrix), and other phases that are too fine to be exactly analysed by the methods employed in this work. For example, some attempts to analyse particles smaller than 3 μm diameter suggest a composition like $\text{Al}_7\text{Cu}_4\text{Ni}$. Table 2 shows the chemical composition of the main microstructures observed in the considered MMC.

Table 2: Results of WDX analysis for Al based MMC with 10 and 20 % SiC particle volume fraction.

Morph.	Likely Phases	Al	Si	Mg	Fe	Mn	Ti	Ni	Cu
Chinese script	Al_3NiCu	61.8± 0.7	1.03± 0.83	0.04± 0.01	0.85± 0.08	0.04± 0.01	0.01± 0.005	19.4± 0.2	16.8± 0.24
Large rounded	$(\text{Al,Cu,Ni})_{15}$ $(\text{Fe,Mn})_3\text{Si}_2$	71.4± 0.54	11.3± 0.37	0.02± 0.007	8.7± 0.064	6.84± 0.26	0.05± 0.066	0.08± 0.148	0.92± 0.226
Dendrites	Al + (Si)	97.7± 0.4	1.47± 0.09	0.16± 0.035	0.02± 0.013	0.03± 0.007	0.01± 0.013	0.06± 0.055	0.52± 0.234
Matrix		66.5± 0.17	30.1± 0.17	0.02± 0.01	0.51± 0.04	0.30± 0.03	0.14± 0.02	0.70± 0.04	1.78± 0.07
SiC particles	SiC	0.30± 0.074	67.8± 0.71	0.01± 0.01	0.04± 0.013	0.02± 0.019	0.00± 0.007	0.06± 0.026	0.14± 0.08

RESULTS

Fatigue crack propagation is strongly affected by the SiC volume fraction, by the SiC particles non-uniform distribution and by the MMC microstructure. Figures 1 and 2 show the fatigue crack propagation in 10% and 20% volume fraction MMC in the $\text{da/dN}-\Delta K$ diagram (i.e. fatigue crack propagation rate-applied stress intensity factor amplitude).

Fig. 1: da/dN - ΔK diagram (10% SiC particles volume fraction, $R=0.5$, 20Hz).

Fig. 2: da/dN - ΔK diagram (20% SiC particles volume fraction, $R=0.5$, 20Hz).

Fatigue crack propagation is characterised by an high dispersion of results in the da/dN - ΔK diagram [6], both for the 10% and the 20% SiC particles volume fractions. Considering the same value of the applied stress intensity factor value, the corresponding fatigue crack propagation rate can change for a factor of one according to the different specimens. This result is probably connected to the non-uniformity in the SiC distribution.

Fatigue crack propagation in da/dN - ΔK diagram is characterised by an evident fluctuation of the experimental points. This fluctuation is connected with the variations in the fatigue crack

direction. This direction can change from the orthogonality to the loading direction to an angle of about $\pm 30^\circ$. This result has been obtained using SEM observations of the lateral crack path after nickeling of the crack surface. Corresponding to each variation in crack propagation direction, fatigue crack propagation rate increase or decrease with a high rate, that can be higher than the rate obtained interpolating the experimental results using the Paris-Erdogan relationship [7].

$$\frac{da}{dN} = C \cdot \Delta K^m \quad (1)$$

where C and m are interpolation coefficients obtained by applying the least square method to the experimental results in the stage II of III.

The phase II of III of fatigue crack propagation, where experimental results have usually a linear behaviour in the log-log diagram $da/dN-\Delta K$, shows a continuous slope variation and the Paris-Erdogan relationship can be used only considering that it could be related with not too high correlation coefficients. Fig. 3 shows the interpolation coefficients "C" and "m" for the fatigue crack propagation in the two considered MMCs.

Fig. 3: Paris-Erdogan relationship interpolation coefficients in the logC-m diagram.

Using a logC-m diagram, considering the same experimental conditions, C-m values have usually a linear behaviour [8-10], and this linear behaviour could be related to the fatigue crack propagation micromechanisms, i.e. striation formation. According to our results, considering the low correlation coefficients of relationship (1), it is not evident that the linear behaviour of logC-m values is correlated with the fatigue crack propagation mechanisms. More results are necessary to obviate the influence of SiC distribution on the stage II of fatigue crack propagation with its peculiar oscillations.

Investigated MMCs show a strongly brittle behaviour, and fatigue crack propagation is affected by the SiC particles presence and distribution. Figures 4 and 5 show two different fracture morphologies, with dendrites inside the fracture (Fig. 4) or secondary cracks (Fig. 5).

Fig. 4: SEM micrograph of the fatigue crack surface: dendrite inside a crack (10% SiC particles volume fraction).

Fig. 5: SEM micrograph of the fatigue crack surface: secondary crack (10% SiC particles volume fraction).

Differences between 10% SiC and 20% SiC are not so evident and surely included in the high statistical dispersion of the results. This is evident in the stage I of III (threshold stage), where a little increasing of ΔK_{th} value with the increasing of SiC volume fraction can be only supposed. Differences in ΔK_{th} values and in the slope m values are probably due to the different influence of crack closure effect [11,12]. This effect can be crack tip plasticity induced, oxide-induced or roughness-induced. Considering that the oxide formation is not SiC particles volume fraction dependent, crack tip plasticity-induced and roughness-induced crack closure effect connected with the formation of significant mode II displacements. The first effect can provide an higher contribution at higher ΔK , the second effect can provide an

important contribution to the role of microstructure in influencing near-threshold crack growth.

SiC volume fraction influence is more evident in the stages II and III. In fact, higher SiC particles volume fractions correspond to higher slope m values. The higher slope m values are also connected to ΔK_{\max} values ($= (1-R)K_{IC}$) that decrease with the increasing of the SiC particles volume fraction. ΔK_{\max} values change from about $6.5 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$, corresponding to 20% SiC particles volume fraction, to about $7.5 \text{ MPa}\cdot\text{m}^{1/2}$, corresponding to 10% SiC particle volume fraction. The higher SiC particles volume fraction corresponds to a more brittle behaviour and to lower values of the toughness K_{IC} .

SiC particles influence on fatigue crack propagation has been investigated using optical observations of the crack surface after nickeling and a partial polishing. Figures 6 and 7 show the result of these observations respectively for the 20 % and the 10% SiC particles volume fraction MMC.

Fig. 6: Optical micrograph of the fatigue crack surface after nickeling and partial polishing (20% SiC particles volume fraction).

It is evident that interfaces metal matrix - SiC particles do not act as preferential path for the fatigue crack propagation that propagates in the metal matrix.

It is possible to calculate the reverse plastic zone r_{rpz} using the following relationship [13]:

$$r_{rpz} = 0.04 \left[\frac{\Delta K}{\sigma_y} \right]^2 \quad (2)$$

Considering the ranges of applied ΔK for the two MMC, r_{rpz} is between about 20 and 100 μm for the 10% of SiC particles and between about 14 and 50 μm for the 20% of SiC particles.

Fig. 7: Optical micrograph of the fatigue crack surface after nickeling and partial polishing (10% SiC particles volume fraction).

These values are comparable with the grain sizes and also with SiC particles dimensions, lesser than 10 μm . However they are lower than the average spacing between SiC particles that can act in the same way as dispersoids, preventing the development of long planar slip bands.

SiC particles can act to deviate crack path, especially considering that the non-uniformity of SiC particles distribution can facilitate this process. The crack path deviation modifies the stress intensity factor situation at crack tip where it could be effective a mixed mode I+II stress intensity factor, and a strong decreasing of fatigue crack propagation is evident. Sudden increasing of the fatigue crack growth rate are connected with an increasing of the component I of the effective stress intensity factor that act at the crack tip. Moreover, the non-uniform SiC particles distribution imply the presence of SiC particles free zones with dimensions that are comparables or higher than the reverse plastic zone. When crack tip meets one or more of

these SiC particles free zones, fatigue crack propagation proceeds via ductile striation forming and a lower fatigue crack growth rate is obtained.

CONCLUSIONS

Al-based MMC with 10% and 20% SiC particles volume fraction microstructure has been investigated. Metal matrix grain size, secondary phase presence and SiC particle distribution have been analysed.

Fatigue crack propagation has been also investigated using CT specimens, considering a stress ratio equals to 0.5 and three fatigue tests for each considered test conditions.

Fatigue crack propagation results are characterised by a high dispersion. Fatigue crack does not propagate at the metal matrix-SiC particles interfaces, but SiC particles non-uniform distribution can participate to deviate the crack path. These deviations are connected with evident oscillations in the results in $da/dN-\Delta K$ diagram and a Paris -Erdogan relationship that can interpolate the experimental results in the stage II only with low correlation coefficients. The influence of SiC volume fraction on fatigue crack propagation is difficult to distinguish to the statistical dispersion. However, more evident differences are shown in stage II and III and they are essentially due to the roughness-induced crack closure effect and to the decreasing of the toughness with the increasing of the SiC particles volume fraction.

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